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F. Liszt's Art of Variation: The Harmony of Spiritual Suffering and Technical Perfection

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Abstract: This article analyzes the artistic and philosophical content of the “art of variation” in the work of F. Liszt and its dialectical harmony with technical perfection. The study shows the principle of thematic transformation (rhythmic, harmonic, textural and coloristic reconstruction of the theme) as the main tool for transferring Liszt’s ideas of spiritual suffering, ascetic contemplation and salvation into musical form. On the example of such works as “Totentanz” (based on Dies Irae), “Bénédiction de Dieu dans la solitude”, “Via crucis” and “Dante Sonata”, the dramatic dynamics of “spiritual suffering” are created through variation-modulation, chromaticism, extended dissonances, register and textural contrasts, as well as the approach of piano virtuosity, pedal technique and texture to orchestral thinking. The article interprets Liszt's late minimalist texture and innovative harmonic language (semitone shifts, undirected tonality) as a form of technical perfection serving a spiritual purpose.

Keywords: art of variation; thematic transformation; spiritual anguish; spirituality; technical perfection; virtuosity; harmonic innovation; chromatics; texture and register contrast; "Totentanz"; "Dante Sonata"; piano technique; programmatic music.

Introduction.

Franz Liszt (1811–1886) — one of the greatest figures in world art and a brilliant representative of the Romantic era’s artistic creativity. In the history of piano art, his name rightfully occupies one of the highest places. As a Hungarian composer, he introduced unique innovations into musical Romanticism, and as a genius-level virtuoso, he gave concerts around the world. Liszt was also a conductor, a talented teacher, a writer, a critic, and a prominent public figure in the field of music.

Liszt’s innovative ideas possessed a visionary character and had a profound influence on the further development of art. Like Robert Schumann, Liszt also wrote music-critical articles and actively promoted the works of Beethoven, Schubert, Mendelssohn, and Wagner. Under his direction, symphonic and operatic orchestras in various countries performed works by Russian composers such as Mikhail Glinka and Anton Rubinstein.

Extensive creative and pedagogical activity. Among the many outstanding pianists who emerged under his influence shine the names of Hans von Bülow, Carl Tausig, Karl Klindworth, Józef Wieniawski, Franz Kroll, and later Moriz Rosenthal, Emil Sauer, Alexander Siloti, Alfred Reisenauer, and Frederic Lamond.

In Liszt’s piano style, the achievements of the composer and the performer are harmoniously united. He once wrote:

“My piano is to me what a frigate is to a sailor, what a steed is to an Arab—perhaps even more; for to this day, my piano is myself, my speech, my life, the intimate guardian of all that stirred my soul in the most passionate days of my youth. Within it lie all my desires, dreams, joys, and sorrows.”

At first, Liszt’s extraordinary performing talent led him to a brilliant career as a piano virtuoso. We will discuss Liszt’s astonishing pianism a bit later, but for

now, let us look at some historical and biographical facts.

Franz Liszt lived during a complex and turbulent era, witnessing many social upheavals. The Great French Revolution occurred almost in the same period as his birth. He was born on the estate of the Esterházy princes. At his christening, his name was written in Latin as *Franciscus*, yet Liszt himself preferred the German form “Franz.”¹

Just like in W. A. Mozart’s biography, Franz Liszt’s first teacher was also his father. His father was a skilled violoncellist, played the spinet (a small harpsichord) with mastery, and was personally acquainted with Joseph Haydn and Johann Nepomuk Hummel.

At the age of nine, Liszt made his first public concert appearance. Later, after moving to Vienna, he studied piano performance with Carl Czerny and music theory and composition with Antonio Salieri. Taking into account the young prodigy’s extraordinary talent and the family’s financial situation, these lessons were given free of charge.

Liszt’s first published work was the “Variations on a Waltz by Diabelli.”²

Later in Paris, Franz Liszt planned to study at the Conservatoire, but his dream did not come true — he was not admitted because he was a foreigner. Nevertheless, he took private composition lessons with A. Reicha, professor at the Paris Conservatoire, and F. Paer, an experienced opera composer. In 1824, his first concert took place at the Italian Theatre in Paris, and the performance ended with tremendous success.

This period coincided with the peak of Napoleon’s power and the subsequent restoration of the monarchy. The July Revolution of 1830 was greeted by the young virtuoso with youthful enthusiasm and idealism. The surrounding social and political atmosphere inspired the composer to heroic pathos, lofty drama, and energetic expression, all characteristic of his musical style.

A significant event in Liszt’s creative biography was his meeting in 1833 with Countess Marie d’Agoult, who published her literary works under the pseudonym Daniel Stern. In 1835, they moved to Switzerland, later traveling through Italy. During these years, Liszt worked intensely and productively — composing, performing, and teaching at the Geneva Conservatory.

In collaboration with Marie d’Agoult, he wrote essays such as “*On the Position of Artists and the Conditions of Their Existence in Society*” and “*Letters of a Bachelor of Music*,” in which they expressed profound reflections on the social significance and aesthetics of art.

¹ The mystical aspect of this choice lies in the fact that it is the name of Saint Francis of Assisi, who in Catholicism personified love for the world and for all living beings, as well as a deep devotion to art, since he himself was a poet. Liszt felt a profound inner connection with him throughout his life, perceiving himself as a wandering poet-preacher. Wishing to draw closer to his saintly patron, Liszt placed an engraving of Saint Francis on his piano in his study. He also dedicated two piano legends to him — “*Saint Francis of Assisi Preaching to the Birds*” and “*Saint Francis of Paola Walking on the Waves*.”

² Anton Diabelli (1781–1858) was an Austrian music publisher and composer, a student of Michael Haydn. In 1822, he invited several well-known composers to write variations on the theme of his waltz. Among those who received such an offer were Ludwig van Beethoven, Franz Schubert, and the young Franz Liszt.

The year 1839 became symbolic for world piano art, as it marked Liszt's first solo recital held in the Roman palace of Russian Prince Golitsyn. Such a performance resembled an orator's monologue, a kind of "*musical soliloquy*" in which the pianist alone was the hero of the evening — communicating his personal vision and emotional interpretation of the works. This event established for the first time the performer's creative primacy as the true creator of living music.

Liszt once declared proudly:

"Like Louis XIV, I could say to the audience: *The concert — it is I!*" [11, p. 227] This demonstrates that Franz Liszt was a reformer not only in composition and pianism, but also in the formation of modern concert traditions. Since then, the performer has been recognized as the central and most influential figure on stage. Liszt's own words further clarify this artistic philosophy:

"A virtuoso is not a stonemason who faithfully chips away at the stone according to the architect's plan. He is not a passive instrument that merely reproduces emotion and thought without adding anything of his own. He is a creator, like the composer himself, for within him must surge the same passions he seeks to express in all their splendor... In truth, a musical work for a virtuoso is a dramatic and moving staging of emotions. He must make them speak, sing, and sigh — according to his own understanding." [5, p. 40]

After that, Liszt's concert activity became even more intense. He performed triumphantly in nearly all European countries and earned the title of "*the greatest pianist in the world.*" I. Moscheles once remarked after attending one of his concerts:

"No one plays like Liszt; after his performance, the piano should be closed forever."

Later, Liszt's performing style underwent significant transformation. Heinrich Heine wrote about this:

"Formerly, when he depicted thunder, we could see lightning flashing across his face; his entire body trembled, and his hair streamed down like newly fallen raindrops. Now, even when performing the mightiest storm, he rises above the scene — like a traveler standing on a mountain peak: below him, clouds gather, lightning flashes like serpents at his feet, and he lifts his head to the clear sky with a smile." [12, p. 99]

In 1842, 1843, and 1847, Liszt gave concerts in Russian cities such as St. Petersburg, Moscow, Kyiv, and Odesa. There he met Mikhail Glinka, Anton Rubinstein, and Alexander Borodin, forming close friendships with several Russian composers. His final concert in Russia took place in 1847; that same year, he left the country for good with Princess Carolyne zu Sayn-Wittgenstein. The fact that Liszt abandoned his concert career at the height of his fame remains a mystery. Perhaps the reason was that, in his pursuit to maintain success, he had begun writing works that pleased audiences with their technical brilliance but lacked deeper artistic substance — a situation that left him personally dissatisfied.

Between 1848 and 1861, Liszt served as *Kapellmeister* at the Weimar court. During this period, he completely withdrew from performing and devoted himself to composition. It was then that he created two symphonies, twelve symphonic poems, numerous vocal and piano works — including the *Années de pèlerinage* cycle, two piano concertos, the *Sonata in B minor*, *Hungarian Rhapsodies*, and many other compositions.

During his Weimar years, Liszt was also active as a conductor (leading the Weimar Opera), a music critic, a teacher, and a public figure. He took an active role in the *General German Music Association*. Thus, even though he had retired from the concert stage, Liszt enriched his creative life further and laid the foundations for many musical innovations.

His spiritual quests eventually led him to a monastic way of life. In 1865, in Rome, he received the title of *Abbé* (cleric). During the 1860s, Liszt divided his time between Rome, Weimar, and Budapest. In 1875, in his homeland of Budapest, he took the initiative to establish the National Academy of Music and was appointed its first president.³

In the 1880s, Liszt resumed his concert activities, though it did not last long. During the Wagner Festival in Bayreuth, he suffered a severe attack of pneumonia and passed away there.

Franz Liszt was one of the most complex and contradictory composers of the Romantic era. However, this complexity does not diminish interest in his art — on the contrary, it enhances it. He was one of the most erudite figures of his time, possessing encyclopedic knowledge in various fields of culture and speaking many European languages. Liszt maintained friendly relations with H. Berlioz, N. Paganini, F. Chopin, V. Hugo, O. de Balzac, H. Heine, A. Mickiewicz, A. Dumas, E. Delacroix, and George Sand (the pseudonym of Aurore Dudevant, close to Chopin).

Just as R. Schumann's musical style reflected the literary spirit of Novalis, Jean Paul, and E.T.A. Hoffmann, Liszt sought to unite different forms of art. He once said: "I learned art not from Czerny, Salieri, Paer, or Reicha, but from Byron, Hugo, and the Saint-Simonians." [11, p. 802]

Throughout his life, Liszt strove for self-discipline and spiritual perfection. He believed that a true musician should be not only an interpreter of lofty feelings and ideas of humanity but also a genuine educator and moral guide.

His inner beliefs were closely aligned with those of Victor Hugo — the idea of unity between art and nature, the harmony of darkness and light, the grotesque and the sublime. For both, true poetry lay in the union of opposites. Liszt once said: "If music alternates between dramatic pathos and melancholy relaxation — it is because the same happens in nature." [12, p. 83]

Liszt's brilliant and innovative creativity transformed the development of piano art. His activity marked the beginning of a new, monumental, and historically significant era in music. While every epoch produced its great

³ Among the many monastic orders, Liszt chose the Franciscan Order of the Minorites, which is associated with the name of Saint Francis of Assisi.

masters, Liszt's entirely new vision of the piano elevated him to a unique position. Many later composers and performers would continue his innovative ideas.

His piano legacy constitutes one of the grandest layers of Romantic musical culture. In both performance and composition, he remained true to his nature and inner world. The Romantic spirit of heroism and "conquest of the stage" found perfect expression in his personality. As S. E. Feinberg aptly observed: "It seems as if the gates to the realm of supreme aesthetic values are fiercely guarded — and one needs courage to enter this domain." [15, p. 101]

These words precisely capture Liszt's creative image — an embodiment of tireless devotion, where the eternal struggle between spiritual and material, divine and demonic forces lives on in his art and performance.

The works written for piano accompanied Liszt throughout his entire life, reflecting the full evolution of his compositional style. In his early pieces, dazzling virtuosity dominates, while in later years it fades, giving way to more complex forms that are less outwardly brilliant yet far deeper in meaning. New tonal colors emerge — reminiscent of the later Impressionists. Liszt elevated his music to the level of complex intellectual, philosophical, and spiritual imagery.

Researchers note that the final period of Liszt's creative life is marked by a strong theological orientation, which uniquely shaped his worldview. The idea of dualism — the inner conflict between two poles, also evident in R. Schumann's works — is vividly expressed in many of Liszt's compositions, particularly in his *Faust Symphony* and *Dante Symphony*. This reflects his philosophy of the world, where opposing forces — the demonic and the "Faustian spirit," the sublime and the spiritual — coexist in dynamic tension.

His style had long embodied theosophical ideas — the eternal struggle between light and darkness, good and evil, hope and destiny, hell and heaven, purity and temptation. These qualities are most clearly manifested in such works as *Sposalizio* ("The Marriage Ceremony"), *Sonetti di Petrarca* ("Petrarch Sonnets"), *Mephisto Waltz*, *Fantasia quasi una Sonata "Après une lecture du Dante"* ("Fantasy-Sonata after Reading Dante"), the *Sonata in B minor*, *Harmonies poétiques et religieuses* ("Poetic and Religious Harmonies"), and *Benediction de Dieu dans la solitude* ("The Blessing of God in Solitude").⁴

There are also other works in which theological and anthropological meanings are intertwined. For example, in the piece "*Totentanz*" (*Dance of Death*), the *Dies Irae* (*Day of Wrath*) theme is convincingly reworked.⁵

In Liszt's earlier and mature periods, the astonishing virtuosity observed in his works also underwent transformation — over time it took on a new character under the influence of lofty artistic ideals. It was no longer mere external brilliance but became a means of expressing inner depth and spiritual exaltation.

The aspect of virtuosity is most vividly manifested in his piano works,

⁴ **Theosophy** (from the Greek *theos* — "God" and *sophia* — "wisdom") means *divine wisdom*; it refers to the supreme knowledge of God and the mystery of divine creation, attained through direct spiritual contemplation or inner perception of divine truth.

⁵ **Theology** (from the Greek *theos* – God and *logos* – teaching) is the study of God, or divine doctrine.

where the close interrelation between composition and performance art is clearly felt. Franz Liszt's finest piano compositions have remained an inseparable part of the concert repertoire of the world's greatest pianists; moreover, they have been firmly incorporated into the curricula of secondary and higher musical institutions, forming the "golden fund" of piano literature.

Liszt's piano creativity not only brought Hungarian culture to global recognition but also became one of the highest peaks of world art. His piano legacy is truly vast. Among his most famous concertos for piano and orchestra are the Piano Concerto No. 1 in E-flat major (1849, revisions in 1853 and 1856) and the Piano Concerto No. 2 in A major (1839, revisions in 1849, 1853, 1857, and 1861). Also noteworthy are the "Pathetic Concerto" for two pianos (later arranged for piano and orchestra), the "Totentanz" (*Dance of Death*), and the "Hungarian Fantasy" — all of which, in terms of content and form, are closely related to the concerto genre.

Among Liszt's major solo piano works that require particular attention are the Sonata in B minor, the Fantasia–Sonata "After Reading Dante", various sets of variations, 19 Hungarian Rhapsodies, the Spanish Rhapsody, the 12 Transcendental Études (Études d'exécution transcendante), 6 Paganini Études, and a number of concert études both with and without specific titles.

Despite the diversity of genres in Liszt's output, each of his works possesses a completely new artistic tone. He reinterpreted such forms as the one-movement piano concerto, the one-movement piano sonata, and the romantic genres of poem, ballade, and fantasy, giving them fresh meaning.

Beyond merely listing well-known works, it is worth noting some less familiar aspects as well. Franz Liszt also composed works for the organ, including the renowned "Fantasy and Fugue on the Theme B–A–C–H." He himself was an accomplished organ performer. In the Altenburg Castle in Weimar (Germany), where he lived, in addition to his favorite Érard grand piano, there was also an unusual pianomélodion — an instrument combining the characteristics of an organ and a piano, equipped with three keyboards, pedals, and several pipe registers.⁶

For this reason, the organ-like manner of performance also found its way into his piano works. In some pieces, Liszt demonstrates the possibility of sustaining several layers of voices simultaneously — in two, three, or even four-stave systems. Examples of this can be found in such works as the "Funeral March," "Grand Solo de Concert," "Mazeppa" Étude, and the transcription of Wagner's *Tannhäuser* Overture.

From this perspective, we can examine the Variations on the theme of Bach's Cantata No. 12 "Weinen, klagen, sorgen, zagen" ("Weeping, Lamentation, Worry, and Doubt"). This work, composed in 1862, was dedicated to Anton

⁶ Sébastien Érard (1752–1831) was a French instrument maker. He built the first piano in France. Together with his brother Jean-Baptiste Érard (1745–1826), he founded a musical instrument factory. Érard also designed the *organ piano* and, in 1821, patented the double escapement mechanism for the piano.

Rubinstein as “a symbol of the deepest respect and friendship.”⁷

Regarding the source: Johann Sebastian Bach composed this cantata in 1714 to a text by the poet S. Franck, intended for performance on the third Sunday after Easter. The motif of the cantata’s opening chorus — precisely the theme chosen by Franz Liszt for his *Variations* — was later incorporated by Bach into the *Crucifixus* section of his Mass in B minor. Thus, the theme has two origins: one in the *Cantata* and the other in the *Mass*.

In the finale of the *Variations*, Liszt uses the chorale “*Was Gott tut, das wohlgetan*” (“What God Does Is Well Done”), taken from the closing chorale of Bach’s cantata.

At the time when Liszt created this work, he had developed a profound interest in Bach’s symbolism. In 1855, he composed the organ piece “*Prelude and Fugue on the Theme B-A-C-H*”, and in 1859, he wrote the piano “*Weinen, Klagen*” *Prelude*.

The term “Basso continuo” in the title also draws attention, since the composition is actually based on the principle of basso ostinato. As researchers have noted, “*the composer skillfully develops the theme through continuous and natural variations of a passacaglia character; what stands out most are the harmonic boldness, chromatic shifts, and contrasts between registers.*” [11, p. 553]

The “*Weinen, Klagen, Sorgen, Zagen*” *Variations* form an integral, monolithic composition in which the boundaries between individual variations are not clearly defined. The theme’s various transformations provide the performer with creative freedom and inspiration. In this sense, Liszt’s variation form ideally reflects the genetic structure of the theme — serving as a model that determines the course of musical movement. Each variation represents a new interpretation of the original model, embodying its transformation and development. Thus, the work expresses an invariant-variational structure — a principle of constant renewal built upon an unchanging foundation:

The *Variations* begin with a majestic and solemn *Andante* introduction.

⁷ In addition to the aforementioned variations, Franz Liszt composed several other works in this genre, including the early *Variations on a Waltz* by A. Diabelli (mentioned at the beginning of the lecture); “*Hexaméron*” (Grand Bravura Variations on the March Theme from Bellini’s opera *I Puritani*); *Seven Brilliant Variations on a Theme* by G. Rossini; *Introduction and Variations on the March Theme* from Rossini’s opera *The Siege of Corinth*; *Five Variations on the Theme “Joseph”* by Méhul; *Eight Variations on an Original Theme*; *Variations on the Theme “Carnival of Venice”* by N. Paganini; and *Variations on the Theme “Tizántúli szép leány.”*

In the articulation, the predominant markings are the “^” symbols (indicating the highest degree of density and accentuation) and “sf” — bright, sharply emphasized accents. These markings prevent the melodic phrases from closing completely; in other words, the motives do not fade away but continue with an inner drive.

The theme is expressed mainly in the upper chordal voices, though it is rhythmically transformed. While in J.S. Bach’s original source the theme moves in $\frac{3}{4}$ meter with a sequence of half and quarter notes, in Franz Liszt’s version this rhythmic structure is doubled in length (that is, 4+2 quarter beats). Moreover, the theme lacks the usual cadence (C–F) at the end; instead, it halts on D-flat and then, through chromatic motion, descends in unison to the lower register.

Simultaneously, in the left hand, an ascending half-step motive in octaves appears. This motive performs a dynamically active function that prevents the theme from fading, while also emphasizing the following harmonic pillars:

$D\flat - C - C\flat - B - B\flat - d\flat - B\flat - d\flat$. After being stated in chords, the theme reappears in pure octaves, yet it does not lose its power, character, or dynamic tension.

In the expositional section, Bach’s theme sounds in close fidelity to the original source. At the end of the introduction, following a demonic trill and a complete cadence in F minor, the theme emerges in the middle register, in the left-hand part, which further intensifies the dramatic energy of the work:

This transition marks a new stage in Liszt’s variation thinking. Here, the logic of development is based not merely on the mechanical transformation of the theme, but on the construction of a dramatically meaningful form. Liszt succeeds in combining architectural structure and improvisatory freedom, emotional expression and formal discipline.

The final section in F major represents catharsis — a symbol of spiritual purification following the tragic intensity of the preceding sections. The shift from the darkness of F minor to the radiance of F major is deeply significant: it embodies Liszt’s artistic philosophy — the idea of seeking light out of darkness, expressed through musical form.

The recitative-like intonation in the finale conveys an inner confession, repentance, and serenity, recalling Liszt’s late spiritual works such as *Via Crucis* and *Miserere*. Here, external virtuosity disappears, giving way to inner sound, contemplation, and spiritual tranquility.

Thus, in Liszt's *Variations*, technical mastery and philosophical depth are harmoniously united, turning the very musical form into a stage for spiritual experience:

The coda consists of two contrasting episodes in terms of tempo: a slow chorale (*Lento*) and a concluding quasi allegro section.

In the chorale theme, stylistic features characteristic of organ performance become evident — as if Liszt imitates the changing of organ registers, that is, the alteration of tone color, by moving from piano dolce (soft and gentle) to *ff* maestoso (loud and majestic).

This transition reflects, in Liszt's music, the process of spiritual elevation and striving toward light: the chorale's calm and peaceful beginning gradually unfolds into a triumphant and radiant conclusion.

Researchers note that Franz Liszt's *Variations on J.S. Bach's "Weinen, klagen, sorgen, zagen"* Cantata is one of the most significant works in the composer's oeuvre. In it, Liszt attains such a profound expression of grief and dramatic intensity that it is scarcely found either in his earlier works or in the creations of his contemporaries [10, p. 109].

When analyzing the *Variations*, it is appropriate to move slightly forward and

briefly address Liszt's technical system, since this large-scale and dramaturgically multilayered composition contains nearly all the principal technical formulas that characterize his pianistic style.

For example, the following passage, though written in relatively subdued dynamics, nevertheless requires a highly developed, brilliant, and expressive technique, fully revealing the maturity and depth of Liszt's pianism.

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